

PHYSICO-CHEMISTRY OF VINYLESTER / GLASS FIBER INTERFACES USED IN SMC COMPOSITES

Thibaut Bénéthuilère^{1,2}, Jannick Duchet-Rumeau¹, Jean-François Gérard¹, Elise Dubost², and Christophe Peyre³

¹Ingénierie des matériaux polymères (IMP) UMR CNRS 5223, INSA Lyon – Université de Lyon.
F-69621 Villeurbanne, France

Email : thibaut.benethuilere@insa-lyon.fr

Email : jannick.duchet@insa-lyon.fr

Email : jean-francois.gerard@insa-lyon.fr

²Plastic Omnium Auto Exterior – Sigmatech.
F-01150 Sainte Julie, France

Email : elise.dubost@plasticomnium.com

³MCR Mixt Composites Recyclables.

F-07302 Tournon sur Rhône, France

Email : christophe.peyre@plasticomnium.com

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, high performance polymer-matrix composites reinforced with glass or carbon fibers are increasingly used for new structural applications in the automotive industry. The objective is to anticipate the future with innovative lightweight concept for significant reduction in CO₂ emissions.

To this end, Sheet Molding Compound (SMC) composites have been extensively used for semi-structural parts such as trunk floor or inner hatchback applications. However the market is more and more demanding innovative structural products (materials) for body in white parts which leads to the development of new SMC solutions. One potential way is the use of vinylester thermosetting polymer together with chopped glass fibers in the SMC formulation. To control the properties of the final composite, one of the key parameters is the interface between the matrix and the reinforcement. The understanding of the mechanical behavior involves an optimized knowledge of this interface at different levels:

- i) The physico-chemical interactions by using the microbond test
- ii) The impregnation by measuring the fibers wettability by the resin
- iii) The composite

In this study, an E-glass fiber was used together with two different vinylester resins. The microbond test was used to characterize the interfacial properties of different joints (fiber, matrix). This micromechanical test is particularly relevant to evaluate the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) whereas mechanical tests on composites are dependent on fiber amount or fiber orientation.

Unidirectional SMC composite samples were processed with the same curing conditions as one used industrially. Short beam shear test was used in order to determine the interlaminar shear stress (ILSS). Post mortem analyses were performed by scanning electronic microscopy (SEM) to evaluate the fracture mechanisms of the interface.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sheet moulding compounds (SMC) are thermoset-based composite materials consisting of an unsaturated polyester or vinylester resin diluted in styrene and thickened with MgO, glass fiber reinforcement and calcium carbonate fillers. Other components can also be added in order to improve mechanical performances, weight lighting and processing of the material. The use of SMC as a high

performance composite in automotive industry is relevant according to their high strength-to-weight properties.

E-glass fibers used for SMC are considered as bundles assembling thousands of having a diameter of about 15 μm . The fiber ability to be wetted by the resin during the impregnation step before and after maturation, as well as after molding is a critical parameter in order to avoid void formation, heterogeneous spreading of the resin outside the bundles (wet-out) but also inside the bundles (wet-through). However, wetting is not the only parameter that has to be taken into account: glass fiber processing and mechanical properties of the interface in terms of stress transfer are of main interest. In order to tailor the physical properties of the resulting SMC composites, it is important to analyze the interfacial phenomena. In fact, the interface is a key component which has a critical influence on the failure mode and toughness of the materials.

As the presence of fillers also creates stress concentration zones in the SMC, the effect of each component must be separated in order to have a better understanding of the role of each individual component. The aim of this study is to develop methodologies that will allow the characterization of the wetting and the impregnation of the glass fibers and the characterization of the interfacial adhesion between the polyester resin and the fiber at micron scale by using the microbond test and at macroscopic scale on unidirectional SMC composites. In order to run such a methodology, a styrene-free resin was considered. Indeed, due to the international considerations about the potential risks of styrene, other alternatives are currently studied. Therefore, replacing styrene by another diluent is becoming more and more critical in order to obtain VOC emission reduction and reduce olfactory constraints, while keeping similar mechanical properties and shrinkage control than standard vinylester resins.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

A commercial E-glass roving was used for the reinforcement of the SMC composites and its properties are listed in Table 1. The non-soluble and soluble fractions in styrene monomer of the fiber sizing were measured.

Two different Sheet Molding Compound (SMC) composite formulations were investigated based on diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A vinylester. Reactive diluent for Resin A was styrene monomer while 1,4-butanediol dimethacrylate (BDDMA) was used for styrene-free Resin B. The SMC used for unidirectional (UD) moulding experiments had the following composition (in wt %): Vinylester in reactive diluent 18.7, low profile additive in reactive diluent 4.7, catalyst 0.4, calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) 23.3, release agent 1.4, magnesia 1.6 and glass fibers 50.0. Formulations without CaCO_3 were also tested.

Fiber	Tex	Sizing (%wt)	Styrene-soluble sizing (%wt)	Comments
1	2,200	1.86 \pm 0.20	0.84 \pm 0.08	Unsaturated polyester & Vinylester-compatible

Table 1 – E-glass Fiber 1 characteristics

Curing and processing conditions

For micromechanical tests, matrices A and B were cured using 1 phr of Methyl Ethyl Ketone Peroxide (MEKP) and 0.02 phr of cobalt octoate accelerator. The cure schedule was 24h at 40°C, 4h at 80°C, 4h at 120°C, and 4h at 180°C. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and Dynamical Mechanical Analysis (DMA) experiments confirmed that the reaction was therefore completed.

UD SMC composites were made of 6 initial layers with dimensions 120 x 250 mm² (covering 100% of the mold surface) and molded at 145°C during 180s at 20 bars. After molding, the thickness of the composites was about 3 mm.

Wettability measurements

In order to evaluate the wettability between the different matrices and fiber, several analyses were performed: dynamic and static wettability measurements (direct measurements) and surface energy measurements (non-direct measurements).

- For the glass fiber surface energy measurements, an Apollo Instruments DCAT 21 Tensiometer was used. Glass fibers were fixed to a support by means of an adhesive tape. Four filaments were used in order to increase the signal-to-noise ratio, and the force on the fiber was measured as the liquid container was raised and withdrawn at a rate of 0.01 mm/s. Three different liquids were used: water, methylene diiodide and ethylene glycol. 10 samples were used for each testing liquid. The contact angle determination with solvents of different polarity is necessary in order to calculate the fiber surface energy and its dispersive and non-dispersive components by using the Owens-Wendt approach¹ (Eq (1)).

$$\frac{\gamma_L \cos(\theta+1)}{2(\gamma_L^D)^{1/2}} = (\gamma_S^{ND})^{1/2} \frac{(\gamma_L^{ND})^{1/2}}{(\gamma_L^D)^{1/2}} + (\gamma_S^D)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where γ_L and γ_S are the SMC paste and glass fiber surface energies, respectively. D and ND refer with their dispersive and non-dispersive components, respectively.

- The surface energy of the thickened SMC paste (before molding) was determined using an Apollo Instruments Digidrop which allows automatic formation of a liquid droplet on the SMC matrix. The wetting liquids used were the same than for the glass fibers and the surface energy was also determined by the Owens-Wendt' equation. The wetting of the fibers by the SMC paste could therefore be evaluated by comparing surface energies and their components and by applying the Zisman criterion².

- The static wettability measurements were performed using a Zeiss optical microscope in reflection mode which allowed the observation of microdroplets deposited on glass filaments (diameter d_f equal to 15 μm). The wettability could then be evaluated by measuring the contact angle between the filament and the droplet, and by calculating the aspect ratio L_e/d , as shown in Fig. 1. These measurements were done before and after curing leading to the determination of the spreading coefficient, denoted S (Eq (3))³, and of the work of adhesion W_{SL} (Eq (4)). This was done by applying the Young-Dupré' equation^{4,5} (Eq (2)).

$$\cos \theta = \frac{\gamma_S - \gamma_{SL}}{\gamma_L} \quad (2)$$

$$S = \gamma_S - (\gamma_{SL} + \gamma_L) \quad (3)$$

$$W_{SL} = \gamma_L(1 + \cos \theta) \quad (4)$$

- Lastly, wettability measurements were completed following the same methodology used for the glass fiber surface energies determination but by using the resin as wetting liquid. Advancing and receding dynamic contact angles were therefore obtained. 8 to 10 samples were tested. These results also gave informations on the chemical heterogeneity and surface roughness of the fibers by considering the hysteresis.

Figure 1 - Vinylester microdroplet deposited on a glass filament

Microbond test

Individual fibers were glued onto a metal holder and polymer droplets were deposited using a copper filament. The entire assembly (Fig.2) was then transferred into an oven for curing. The cure schedule was the one reported above. Until reaching the gelation time, the atmosphere was saturated with styrene in a closed enclosure in order to avoid styrene evaporation from the microdroplets. After curing and cooling down to room temperature, the samples were prepared from symmetric droplets and the filaments were glued onto triangular paper holders which were mounted in a tensile machine with 10 N load cell. Embedded length, droplet diameter, contact angle, and fiber diameter were measured using an optical microscope in order to calculate the interfacial shear stress denoted IFSS, and to characterize the wettability after curing.

Figure 2 - Microbond test: Individual fibers with microdroplets on metal holder (left side) & schematic illustration of the test (right side)

The system used to perform the microbond test consisted of two cutter blades mounted on a movable block that were controlled with micrometer screws (Fig.2). A macroscopic camera was used to help positioning the cutter blades and to monitor the test. The displacement rate was set to 0.1 mm/min. The fiber was pulled-out of the droplet blocked by the cutter blades and the load-displacement was recorded for each test until debonding occurred. The maximum force at debonding, F_{max} , was considered together with the interfacial area in order to calculate the interfacial shear stress⁶ as shown in Eq. (5) i.e. taking into account a constant shear stress along the embedded length. 20 to 30 single tests were performed for each couple fiber/matrix in order to obtain an averaged IFSS. The debonding zone was observed using an optical microscope and a scanning electron microscope (SEM) to verify the validity of the test: no residual resin must be left behind the fiber. Examples of debonding profile are shown in Fig.3.

$$\tau = \frac{F_{max}}{\pi L_e d_f} \quad (5)$$

where F_{max} is the maximum force, L_e is the embedded length and d_f is the glass filament diameter.

Figure 3 - SEM photograph of different debonded fiber surfaces (Resin A): cohesive failure of the matrix (left side) and adhesive failure of the fiber/matrix interface (right side)

Short-beam shear test

The unidirectional SMC long E-glass fiber/vinylester composites were tested using the short-beam shear test. The bending beam specimens were cut directly from the composite plate. The dimensions were chosen in order to enhance shear stress in the neutral fiber plane (vs. tension/compression modes on the external planes), i.e. for having only shear failure. Thus the length-to-sample thickness ratio, denoted as λ , was set below 5^{7,8}, and the displacement rate for the bending test was 1 mm/min. The load-displacement was recorded for each test until failure and the maximum force at interlaminar fracture, F_{max} , was used in order to determine the interlaminar shear stress, ILSS, as shown in Eq. (6).

$$ILSS = \frac{3F_{\max}}{4bt} \quad (6)$$

where b and t are the thickness and width of the sample, respectively.

ILSS which characterizes interlaminar shear stress, i.e. at macro scale, was compared to IFSS values, i.e. at micron scale, for different fiber/resin combinations considered for SMC composites.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Determination of wettability criteria

A good wetting is necessary in order to achieve an intimate interfacial contact between the fiber and the matrix. In SMC composites, the impregnation step (wet-through and viscosity) during calandering is another key parameter and will also determine the final properties of the composite. Nevertheless a perfect wetting is the first step in order to improve the final properties of the fiber/matrix interface by increasing the thermodynamic work of adhesion.

- *Glass fiber surface energy*

The results obtained thanks to Owens-Wendt' equation are presented in Fig. 4. Sized glass fibers are still polar, with a non-dispersive component close to 15 mN/m. This is explained by the nature of the sizing covering the fiber surface in order to prevent water, favorable interactions with the matrix, and processability. On the opposite, SMC pastes are not polar. In order to quantify the wettability of the glass fibers with the SMC resins, the Zisman's empiric wetting condition can be considered: the fiber surface could be wet by the SMC paste if their surface energy is higher than the one of the SMC paste. The wettability criteria should as well be improved from taking into account the dispersive and non-dispersive components of the fibers. If these ones are close to those of the SMC, favorable interactions will take place leading to wettability. Based on the results obtained in this work, it can be concluded that the fibers will be easily wet by the SMC paste. However, an optimized wetting seems to be obtained for the conventional SMC system compared to the styrene-free reactive system. This phenomenon could be due to the fully dispersive nature of the styrene-free paste surface, while the glass fibers have a much higher polar characteristic.

Figure 4 - Surface energies of E-glass fibers and SMC systems (before curing)

- *Wetting and dewetting contact angles*

By bringing directly into contact the unreacted resin and the fiber, it was possible to obtain directly advancing and receding contact angles. Receding contact angles were always observed to be zero showing favorable interactions between the fiber surface and the vinylester matrix. It also confirmed the high chemical heterogeneity and roughness of the fiber surface. Advancing contact angles reported in Table 2 and are the same for the two types of SMC resins.

Advancing contact angle (°)	
Resin A	37 ± 4
Resin B	37 ± 4

Table 2 - Advancing contact angle of vinylester resin (uncured) systems on E-glass fiber

- *Static contact angles*

Fig. 5 reports the contact angles obtained before curing for micro droplets of non-polymerized vinylester resins on glass filaments. It is observed a linear increase of the contact angle with the embedded length. This can be explained by the heterogeneity of the sizing layer on the fiber surface. Contact angles measured on unsized fibers usually show a lower variability⁹. But it can also be explained by the incorrect measurement of contact angles. Indeed, the reported measurements were done by considering the direct angle formed by the vinylester droplet deposited on a glass fiber. However, measuring the contact angle at the meniscus without using numerical methods as the one proposed by H. D. Wagner⁸ was almost impossible and obviously led to reading error when measuring this contact angle “manually” with the optical microscope. While keeping in mind that the measured angle is not the true angle, it can still be used in order to compare the wettability between both resins.

Figure 5 - Contact angle dependence with the embedded length for the two types of E-glass / vinylester resin interfaces

Averaged contact angles were calculated for an embedded length of about 100 μm (Table 3). From both vinylester resins (see Fig. 5 and Table 3), it is clear that the styrene-free resin has a lower wetting ability than the conventional resin. This result confirms the ones obtained from a theoretical calculation of the spreading coefficient from the surface energies of the components (confirmed from L_c/d shape factor of the microdroplet for the same given embedded length).

	Embedded Length (μm)	Contact angle θ (°)	L_c/d
Resin A	103 ± 12	23.7 ± 3.6	2.01 ± 0.14
Resin B	102 ± 14	31.1 ± 4.8	1.74 ± 0.14

Table 3 - Contact angles and aspect ratio of microdroplet for both resins A and B deposited on E-glass fiber 1 for a given embedded length

The spreading parameter is in both cases negative meaning that the wetting is partial which is obvious as the resin does not spread completely. However the results obtained and shown in Fig. 6 confirm again that wetting is improved when styrene is used. Indeed, one can see that when the styrene-free vinylester resin is used, the spreading parameter decreases (becomes more negative) and the work of adhesion decreases too. The work of adhesion is calculated here for a hypothetical composite interface where only dispersive (London' types) and electron acceptor-donor (Lewis' acid-base) interactions are involved. In our case, this is not the case as there are covalent interactions

between the sizing and the vinylester matrix, as well as dissolution and swelling of the sizing by the matrix could occur during impregnation and curing.

Figure 6 - Work of adhesion and spreading coefficient for the two types of vinylester resin/E-glass fiber interfaces

Changes of the wettability as a low profile additive (LPA) was added were also observed. As shown in Fig. 7, the shape factor (L_c/d_f) decreases in both cases after curing due to resin shrinkage. However, this effect does not change the previously reported results showing better wetting when styrene was used instead of BDDMA in vinylester formulation. These results seem to demonstrate a slightly lower wettability of the resin as a low profile additive is incorporated in styrene-based vinylester Resin A. This is corrected after curing since there is a balance between shrinkage and wettability.

Figure 7- Wettability changes before and after curing as well as in the presence of low profile additive (PVAc) for the two types of vinylester matrices

All measurements lead to the same conclusion, i.e. a better wetting of the fibers when vinylester Resin A is used. This was confirmed by the direct observation of the SMC paste after calandring as shown in Fig. 8. In both cases, the wet-out seems very good, while the wet-through seems more difficult in the case of styrene-free Resin B, i.e. the bundles remain integrate.

Figure 8 - UD SMC pastes after calandring: Fiber 1 Resin A (left-side) & Fiber 1 Resin B (after "scratching") (right-side)

Adhesion measurements

In order to analyze the interfacial adhesion data obtained from the microbond test, the average IFSS (interfacial shear stress from a Kelly-Tyson' model) was calculated according to Equation 5. This approach is of great interest as it allows a direct comparison between the different fiber/matrix interfaces. Additional micromechanical analyses of the data will be reported in another paper.

Due to a high level of interfacial adhesion between glass fiber surfaces and thermoset matrices, the microdebonding test cannot be performed when embedded length are higher than 200 μm as only matrix or fiber breakages occur. Fig. 9 represents the debonding force as a function of embedded length for both resins. The scattered data are inherent to this kind of test which involves many experimental parameters.

It can be seen from Fig. 9 that the two interfaces cannot be differentiated in terms of critical embedded length, which is slightly lower than 200 μm in both cases. Interface behaviors are also similar since the debonding force linearly increases with the embedded length according to a close dependency.

Figure 9 - Debonding force as a function of embedded length for vinylester Resin A / Fiber 1 (left side) and styrene-free vinylester Resin B / Fiber 1 interfaces (right side)

IFSS results are reported in Fig. 10 and compared to shear yield stress of the vinylester matrix (which is similar for both resins). As expected, the IFSS do not exceed the shear yield stress which means that the stress transfer between the matrix and the fiber could be improved. As improved interfaces for vinylester matrix A could be expected from wettability measurements, slightly higher

interfacial shear strength is noticed for the styrene-free vinylester matrix/E-glass fiber interface. This result demonstrates that the wettability criteria is required initially but is not sufficient to get an improved bond strength.

Figure 10 – Determination of IFSS for both resins and comparison with the shear yield stress of the vinylester matrices

As a low profile PVAc additive (LPA) is added to the formulation, no significant changes were observed in terms of stress transfer between the matrix and the fiber. Considering the fracture surfaces shown in Fig. 11, it is easy to see the vinylester matrix ability to plastically deform when subjected to the cutter blades compression contact. Even if this phenomenon is common for thermoplastic matrices, it was also observed by P. Zinck & al.¹⁰ for epoxy matrix/E-glass fiber interfaces. As the IFSS calculation considers purely linear elastic analysis, this means that the interface toughness is over-estimated due to energy consumption in plastic deformation under the blades. The presence of a residual meniscus shows that the failure is initiated according to a Mode-I in the meniscus and then propagated in a Mode-II along the interface. No differences could be observed as the LPA is added.

Fibre 1 – Resin A

Fibre 1 – Resin A + LPA PVAc

Figure 11 - SEM micrographs of fracture interfaces after debonding

It should be mentioned that Greszczuk's¹¹ stress criterion model and Penn & Lee's^{12,13} energy model were also considered to analyze these micromechanical data. Unfortunately, due to the linear increase of the debonding force with the embedded length it was not possible to fit the experimental

data. This can be explained by the very narrow range of embedded length which can be considered to perform the microdebonding test (from 70 to 180 μm), due to the existence of a very strong interface established from covalent bonding between the sized E-glass surface and the matrix. In another study considering carbon fibers, it was possible to fit the experimental data with the Greszczuk' and Penn & Lee' models thanks to the lower interfacial adhesion.

Unidirectional SMC Composites

Before performing mechanical tests, all the characteristics of the UD composites, i.e. density (which allows to evidence of porosities) and glass fiber volume fraction were determined. Table 4 combines both these characteristics and mechanical properties determined from flexural test. When maturation was completed, porosities appeared on the SMC material when styrene-free Resin B was used. This was even more evident when no fillers were used (Fig. 12). These porosities remained effective after molding without CaCO_3 , but disappeared with CaCO_3 : i.e. calcium carbonate contributed to fill the porosities. This phenomenon can be explained by the lower wettability of the styrene-free resin observed at microscopic scale. As the sizing of the E-glass Fiber 1 was developed for polyester and vinylester resins with high styrene solubility, fibers with a different sizing could contribute to improve the wettability and therefore to remove the porosities.

Sample	Shrinkage (%)	C=C conversion (%)	Glass fiber (wt%)	Glass fiber (vol%)	3-point bending 0°		
					Modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Strain at break (%)
Fiber 1 Resin A with CaCO_3	0.08	98	51.8 \pm 1.7	38.3	29 \pm 1	1031 \pm 43	3.5 \pm 0.3
Fiber 1 Resin B with CaCO_3	0.09	96.5	51.9 \pm 1.1	37.4	28 \pm 2	866 \pm 63	3.4 \pm 0.3
Fiber 1 Resin A without CaCO_3	0.11	95.5	53.8 \pm 0.2	33.0	26 \pm 1	800 \pm 35	3.4 \pm 0.2
Fiber 1 Resin B without CaCO_3	0.08	96.5	51.3 \pm 0.7	30.2	25 \pm 2	657 \pm 76	2.9 \pm 0.2

Table 4 - Unidirectional SMC composites properties

Figure 12 - SMC paste before molding: Resin B with CaCO_3 (left-side) and Resin B without CaCO_3 (right-side)

The interlaminar shear stresses obtained for the different UD composites are reported in Fig. 14. As the volumic fraction of E-glass fiber are similar, it is possible to discuss the mechanical properties of the different composite materials. Interlaminar shear stresses allow to analyze the interfaces between the fiber and Resin A or styrene-free Resin B. Even if calcium carbonate fillers improve the SMC composite modulus (due to their elevated modulus), they also creates defects and/or voids, i.e. stress concentration zones close to the interfaces (Fig. 13) leading to decrease the ILSS. In fact, in both cases the ILSS is significantly lower compared to the IFSS values obtained with the microbond test for the two vinylester matrices which did not contain any fillers. Besides the observations that were made at microscopic scale are not the same on the composite: the stress transfer between matrix and fiber is not improved when the styrene-free Resin B is used. This is more in correlation with all the wettability

observations. This phenomenon could be linked to the styrene evaporation at microscopic scale, leading to an underestimation of the IFSS results with styrene-containing Resin A.

When calcium carbonate is not introduced in the vinylester resins (Fig. 14), the ILSS value obtained for Resin A is closer from the one obtained on microcomposites including the values from the literature^{14,15,16}.

Figure 13 - Influence of calcium carbonate on the interface: Fiber 1 / Resin A with fillers (left-side) and without fillers (right-side)

This also highlights the negative effect of the fillers on the interface as reported before. For styrene-free Resin B, the value remains very low which confirms the wetting observations: even if the intimate contact between Fiber 1 and Resin B is ensured at microscopic scale, the wet-through is not sufficient to allow Resin B to migrate inside the bundles. Further studies are ongoing to evaluate the SMC composites using chopped glass fibers.

Figure 14 - ILSS of UD composite materials based on vinylester matrices which include fillers (left-side) and without fillers (right-side)

IV. CONCLUSION

In the present work, the potential of styrene-free resin on the impregnation and adhesion levels of SMC composites was evaluated. In that matter styrene was replaced by 1,4-butanediol dimethacrylate in vinylester resin, and a vinylester/polyester compatible glass fiber was used. The sizing was highly soluble in styrene. Wettability analyses revealed high differences between the two resins. In accordance with the SMC process observations, styrene-free Resin B displays a lower ability than

Resin A to wet E-glass fiber having vinylester-compatible sizing. For the two types of vinylester systems, the wetting was ensured as it was confirmed at microscopic scale by using wettability measurements. These measurements allowed quantifying the wet-out on the fiber. However, the wet-through inside the glass fiber bundles was only observed after calandering.

Micromechanical analysis showed a better stress transfer from the matrix to the fiber by using the styrene-free Resin B. As BDDMA is far less volatile than styrene, the difference of IFSS values obtained from the two types of vinylester matrices using the microdroplet debonding test could be influenced. By considering unidirectional composites it was clear evidenced that the compatibility between Fiber 1 and styrene-free Resin B needs to be improved. Short-beam flexural test allowing to quantify ILSS showed significant difference between Resin A and Resin B (-11% with fillers and -32% without when Resin B was used). The use of fillers also led to a decrease of interfacial properties by incorporating porosities close to the interface, i.e. stress concentration.

All the analyses developed to compare two types of vinylester resin used in SMC formulations showed the limits of styrene-free resin in terms of wettability and adhesion. These observations still need to be confirmed on chopped glass fibers SMC composites. Further analysis will also include others commercial glass fibers.

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